

BEHBUDIYNI KIM O'LDIRGAN?

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Annotatsiya. Behbudiy – jadidchilik harakati arbobi va ma'rifatparvar ziyolilardan biri, Turkistonning ma'rifiy va ijtimoiy taraqqiyoti yo'lida muhim ishlar qilgan shaxsdir. Uning faoliyati zamonaviy ta'lim tizimini shakllantirish, milliy matbuotni rivojlantirish va xalqni uyg'otishga qaratilgan edi. Behbudiy qotilligi esa o'sha davrning siyosiy va ijtimoiy ziddiyatlaridan kelib chiqqan murakkab hodisadir. Ushbu maqola Behbudiyning o'ldirilishi sabablarini, zamonaviy tarixiy nuqtai nazardan tahlil qiladi va uning faoliyatini o'sha davr kontekstida yoritishga harakat qiladi. Qotillikning asosiy omillari sifatida diniy va siyosiy qarama-qarshiliklar, shuningdek, jadidlarning kuchayishi natijasida vujudga kelgan keskinliklar ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Jadidchilik, ma'rifat, yangi usul maktablari, gazeta, jurnal.

Аннотация. Бехбудий — деятель джадидского движения и один из просветителей интеллигенции, человек, проделавший большую работу по образовательному и общественному развитию Туркестана. Его деятельность была направлена на формирование современной системы образования, развитие национальной прессы и пробуждение народа. Убийство Бехбуди — сложное событие, возникшее в результате политических и социальных конфликтов того времени. В статье анализируются причины убийства Бехбуди с точки зрения современной истории и делается попытка осветить его деятельность в контексте той эпохи. Основными факторами, приведшими к убийству, были названы религиозные и политические конфликты, а также напряженность, возникшая в результате усиления джадидов.

Ключевые слова: джадидизм, просвещение, новометодные школы, газета, журнал

Abstract. Behbudiy is a figure of the Jadid movement and one of the enlightened intellectuals, a person who did important work for the educational and social development of Turkestan. His activities were aimed at forming a modern education system, developing the national press, and awakening the people. The murder of Behbudiy is a complex event arising from the political and social conflicts of that time. This article analyzes the reasons for the murder of Behbudiy from a modern historical perspective and tries to shed light on his activities in the

context of that time. The main factors of the murder are religious and political contradictions, as well as tensions arising as a result of the rise of Jadidism.

Keywords: *Jadidism, enlightenment, new method schools, newspaper, magazine.*

Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy uyg'onish davri o'zbek adabiyotida birinchi o'rinni olishga loyiq zotdir.

Xoja Muin ibn Shukrullo

Maxmudxo'ja Behbudiy (1875–1919) — jadidchilik harakatining asoschilaridan biri, o'zbek ma'rifatchi va adiblaridan biri. U o'z asarlari, ijtimoiy faoliyati va jadidchilik islohotlari orqali Turkiston xalqlarini ma'rifatli qilish va milliy uyg'onishga chaqirdi. Behbudiyning o'limi uning hayotiy kurashi va faoliyati bilan bevosita bog'liq bo'lgan murakkab tarixiy sharoitning natijasi sifatida yuzaga kelgan. Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy 1875-yilda Samarqandda ziyoli oilada tug'ilgan. Yoshligidan ilmga qiziqib, o'sha davrdagi madrasa ta'limini olgan. Ammo an'anaviy ta'lim tizimining kamchiliklarini tushunib, zamonaviy ta'limni joriy etish g'oyasini ilgari surgan.

Shu maqsadda Behbudiy yangi usul maktablarini tashkil qilishga kirishgan va xalqni savodsizlikdan qutqarish uchun astoydil harakat qilgan.[1]

Behbudiy va jadidchilik harakati

Jadidchilik harakati XIX asr oxiri va XX asr boshlarida Turkiston hududida yuzaga kelgan.

Uning asosiy maqsadi millatni savodli qilish, ilm-fanni rivojlantirish va madaniy islohotlar orqali xalqni zamonaviylashishga olib kelish edi. Behbudiy bu harakatning eng faol vakillaridan bo'lib, u yangi usul maktablari tashkil qilish, gazeta va jurnallar nashr qilish, shuningdek, ijtimoiy-siyosiy masalalarda faol qatnashdi.

So'nggi yillarda Behbudiy o'limi sirlarini o'rganish bilan faol qiziqqan va bir necha maqolalarni e'lon qilgan jurnalist va adabiyotshunos Halim Saidning yozishicha, Behbudiyning g'oyib bo'lganligi haqidagi ilk rasmiy xabar ular chiqib ketganlaridan bir oy keyin "Mehnatkashlar tovushi" gazetasining 1919-yil 23 aprel, ikkinchi xabar esa o'sha yilning 20-noyabr sonlarida berilgan. So'nggi xabarda, jumladan, e'tiborga molik bunday ma'lumotlar bo'lgan: "Temurxon afandi (Halim Sayidning yozishicha, Birinchi jahon urushi arafasida Istanbulga o'qishga borgan samarqandlik – N.K.) bergan ma'lumotga ko'ra, Behbudiy afandi Samarqanddan chiqib, Buxoro muzofotidan hibsi qiling'oni hamon bu xabar Bokuda shoyi' (ma'lum) bo'lg'on. Bokuda turg'uvchi turkistonlik Said Nosir ismli bir zot bir vosita topib, Buxorodan Behbudiy haqida ma'lumot so'rab, taxlisi (xalos qilish) uchun ko'shish (harakat) qilg'on. Lekin bu haqda Buxorodan hech bir xabar ola olmag'on.

Bu mavsuq (aniq) xabardan ma'lum bo'lurki, mundin burunroq Moskvadan kelib, "Ishtirokiyun" gazetasi idorasida "Behbudiy afandi Qofqozda ekan", deb xabar bergan.[2]

Maxmudxo'ja Behbudiy 1919-yilning 25-mart kuni Samarqand yaqinida bosmachilar tomonidan qatl etilgan. Uning o'ldirilishiga asosiy sabab sifatida uning jadidchilik g'oyalari va bosmachilik harakatiga qarshi tanqidiy fikrlari keltiriladi. Behbudiy xalqni savodsizlikdan qutqarish va islohotlar orqali millatni rivojlantirishga chaqirar edi. Biroq, bosmachilar uning bu qarashlarini Rossiya hukmronligini qo'llab-quvvatlash sifatida talqin qilgan.

Bosmachilar va jadidlar o'rtasidagi qarama-qarshilik

Bosmachilik harakati, asosan, Turkistondagi sovet hokimiyatiga qarshi kurashgan qurolli guruhlarni o'z ichiga olgan. Ular o'z harakatlarini milliy ozodlik kurashi deb e'lon qilgan bo'lsalar-da, ba'zan jadidlar kabi intellektual guruhlar bilan qarama-qarshilikka kirishgan.

Behbudiyning jadidchilik g'oyalari bosmachilar uchun xavfli bo'lib ko'rindi, chunki bu g'oyalar jamiyatni yangicha yo'nalishga olib chiqish imkoniyatiga ega edi.

Behbudiyning o'limining sabablari

Behbudiyning o'ldirilishi bir necha omillar bilan bog'liq:

1. Ijtimoiy-siyosiy qarashlar: Behbudiyning jadidchilik qarashlari bosmachilar tomonidan Sovetlar bilan hamkorlik qilish sifatida noto'g'ri talqin qilingan.

2. Diniy qarama-qarshiliklar: Jadidchilik islomni yangicha talqin qilishni taklif qilganligi sababli, ayrim diniy guruhlar orasida bu qarashlar dushmanlikni keltirib chiqardi.

3. Bosmachilarning siyosiy strategiyasi: Bosmachilar jadidlarni o'z harakatlariga tahdid sifatida ko'rgan va ularning yetakchilarini nishonga olishni maqsad qilgan.

Maxmudxo'ja Behbudiy o'z davrining ilg'or va ma'rifatparvar shaxslaridan biri edi. Uning o'ldirilishi jadidchilik harakatining qiyin sharoitlarda qanday kurash olib borganini ko'rsatadi. Behbudiy millatni ma'rifat orqali rivojlantirishni o'zining hayotiy maqsadi deb bilgan va bu yo'lda o'z hayotini qurbon qilgan. Bugungi kunda Behbudiy merosi o'zbek milliy uyg'onish harakati tarixida katta ahamiyatga ega.

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